

USING SCIENCE FOR/IN DIPLOMACY
FOR ADDRESSING GLOBAL CHALLENGES

The Impact Story of S4D4C

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WE EXPLORED AND INFORMED EU SCIENCE DIPLOMACY

Networks
and dialogue

Governance
framework

Knowledge
resources

Trainings for
science diplomats

1. Introduction

The overall aim of S4D4C is to support current and future European science diplomacy (SD) for the benefit of European capacities, EU foreign policy goals and especially the development of solutions for global challenges¹. This report was developed around the six underlying project objectives, which form the core of the monitoring system. At the end of the project's duration (in April 2021) we are able to address our contributions considering the long-term impact of the project "Using science for/in diplomacy for addressing global challenges" (S4D4C).

The project's work touched upon various contexts related to SD. The interdisciplinary and social sciences research on SD explored the needs and experiences of its stakeholders and analysed actual cases of SD (case studies). Building on the research work, a government framework and further policy advice was provided. Several training events as well as training materials were developed. Through outreach activities and networking the project engaged globally and fostered an SD community.

The report reflects on initially expected outcomes and effects, but also considers outcomes and impacts that were not anticipated at the beginning of the project. For one, the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted shortcomings in the current

interaction between international relations and scientific cooperation and thus sparked a growing interest in ongoing S4D4C work within the wider SD community. This in turn, led to increased interest in the role of science, science advice to international policy and SD and thus to S4D4C's topics and outputs. We quickly formed a task force and compiled a policy brief related to the COVID-19 pandemic. This also influenced several other publications, such as one on future training on SD for global challenges².

Due to increasing attention of the scientific community on the SD topic our project has received unexpected reactions and support, such as an article on the S4D4C website by European Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth Mariya Gabriel (Gabriel, 2020). Within the context of training activities, the lack of easily accessible training offers was manifest by the fact that our courses have been either overbooked (on-site trainings) or were embraced (Online Course on European SD) by more than 6000 individuals who signed up for it. This led to some additional actions that were not originally included in the project, like the S4D4C interactive webinar series that we organised in the second half of 2020.

1 see: <https://www.s4d4c.eu/about/project-description/>

2 Meyer et al.: A New Generation of Trainings on Science Diplomacy for Global Challenges: Insights from two European Projects, in: Science Diplomacy Review, Issue of March 2021 (forthcoming).

2. Impact Monitoring in S4D4C

S4D4Cs impact-oriented monitoring system follows an intervention logic, activity clusters and key performance indicators (KPIs) as well as timelines, roles and implementation patterns set out at the beginning of the project.

Project Intervention Logic

S4D4Cs logical intervention framework is based on the six project objectives³:

1. New insight and better understanding of contribution of science/science cooperation/ SD to foreign policy goals
2. Facilitation of effective and efficient interfaces for European SD
3. Policy guidance for future SD areas
4. Preparation for European SD for better profile and stronger identity
5. Increased capacities and knowledge resources
6. Global reach and visibility

These objectives were operationalised on activity-, output-, outcome- and impact-level. Activities were identified at task level and included processes, tools, events and other actions that were an intentional part of the programme implementation. Outputs are the technical, tangible results or products of the planned activities whereas outcomes represent the direct effects of the project. Finally, impacts are the long-term or indirect effects of the outcomes. This operationalisation of the project translated the six project objectives into a work plan. It facilitated the impact-oriented execution of the project and served as an internal working tool for the impact manager and project partners.

Activity clusters and key performance indicators (KPIs)

S4D4C activities were clustered into five main groups of activities: the production of text

documents, training courses, exchange and networking, the preparation of knowledge resources as well as S4D4C appearances on external platforms and in social media channels. For each activity cluster a specific set of indicators was identified in order to measure the output and outcomes with regard to the overall objectives of the project. Table 1 shows a small selection of quantitative data that we collected over time.

Although indicators are limited in showing the quantifiable use of the project's results, they turned out to be valuable in terms of indicating impacts. There is one indicator that we missed at the beginning of the project: "country of origin" of our users and participants. This indicator is missing in our statistical analysis of events, workshops etc. But it became very clear, and most strongly after we started the online training course, that this was a factor of importance, as global participation in our activities surpassed our expectations in quantity and quality. The data we have on geographical distribution of participants in the activity clusters S4D4C trainings and S4D4C exchange and networking is thus incomplete.

3 For more information see: <https://www.s4d4c.eu/about/project-description/>

Table 1: Clusters of S4D4C activities and indicators (selection)

S4D4C text documents and other formats	Download numbers from project website	Number of published items	Participation in events where content was presented
Research and policy papers	14133	23	55+
S4D4C trainings	Number of participants	Gender Ratio (via evaluation form)	Professional background of participants (via evaluation form)
Vienna 2019	25	Female: 64% Male: 36% Rather not say: 0%	Diplomats or public service: 64% Scientists: 24% Others: 12%
Online Course (from 2020)	6000	Female: 51% Male: 47% Rather not say: 2%	Civil Service Official: 5,6% Diplomat: 6% Science adviser: 3,6% Science manager or administrator: 9,2% Scientist with no diplomatic role: 39,2% Scientist with some diplomatic responsibilities: 5,4% Other: 30,6%
S4D4C exchange and networking	Number of number participants	Scientific background of participants (via evaluation form)	Professional background of participants (via evaluation form)
1st Goba Meeting Madrid 2018	150	Engineering and technology: 7,7% Humanities: 7,7% Medical and health sciences: 7,7% Natural sciences : 38,5% Social sciences: 38,5%	Manager/administrator: 7,7% Science advisor: 23,1% Scientist with no diplomatic role, but interested in diplomatic issues: 38,5% Scientist with some diplomatic responsibilities: 15,4% Other: 15,4%

S4D4C text documents and other formats	Download numbers from project website	Number of published items	Participation in events where content was presented
Final Networking Event (virtual)	765	Agricultural Sciences: 4,2% Engineering and Technology: 11,5% Medical and health sciences: 10,4% Natural sciences: 15,6% Social sciences, humanities, other: 40,6% Mixed: 15,6%	Diplomat: 7,3% Manager or administrator: 21,9% Science advisor: 14,6% Scientist with no diplomatic role, but interested in diplomatic issue: 30,2% Scientist with some diplomatic responsibilities: 12,5% Other: 14%
S4D4C knowledge resources	Number of published items on website	Number of clicks on the main training material page	Number of downloads for the most visited Training Material
Training Material	24	2125	160
S4D4C Social Media	Tweets and Replies	Likes	Followers
Twitter	1186	29826	3304

Source: Own compilation

We additionally asked participants of training opportunities, events and workshops for qualitative assessment (via surveys) of our activities and also did the same in a final survey with regard to our analytical outputs (publications) (e.g. "Did you gain new insights? Will you apply the newly acquired knowledge? Which of the following S4D4C activities and results are you aware of and how useful do you perceive them?"). Some of these results are displayed in chapter 3.

Impact dimensions

S4D4C is built towards a set of long-term impacts which mirror the dedication and ambition of the S4D4C team:

- Stronger EU position in the global context
- Realization of the EUs contribution to the solution of global challenges
- Stable and productive diplomatic relations with the EUs international partners
- Enhanced cooperation between EU, its Member States and international partners
- Better contribution of SD to EU foreign policy
- Improvement of the global response to societal challenges
- Turning excellent science, technology and innovation into solutions for global challenges

Although being very desirable, those impacts are clearly not possible to achieve fully within the life-time of a research project on science diplomacy. They are long-term developments that can be initiated, but need to be driven by different institutions,

alliances and policies to become manifest. We stated in the impact monitoring concept, that an assessment of the overall impact of the project activities will not be possible within the timeframe of the project itself. Impacts take time to become visible and measurable and they can often directly or unequivocally be connected to project outputs.

In order to get evidence about project effects during the runtime of the project, the monitoring focused mainly on the activity-, output- and outcome-level. An overview of S4D4C outputs is displayed in the Annexes 1-8.

A more qualitative story telling approach provides a better picture of where we believe the impacts are. We thus decided to focus on certain already visible impact highlights that we understand as milestones on the pathways to impact dimensions. Viewed over time, those impact highlights might be the spark that initiate change (or contribute to it) and will feed into those desired developments. We are aware that this approach is self-assessing to a certain degree. Therefore, an independent ex-post evaluation several years after the project would be interesting in terms of measurable impact and provide independent views.

We identified the following five impact highlights:

Generating new knowledge and enriching the academic debate on Science Diplomacy

Making practical knowledge on Science Diplomacy available

Raising a global Science Diplomacy Community & fostering alliances between stakeholders

Shaping national and regional Science Diplomacy policies

Advancing European Science Diplomacy

The basis for the identification of these were – amongst others - the visibility of our activities and the responsiveness at policy and institutional level. In addition, the responses of the community to and take-up of our activities supported these highlights.

This document reflects on the effects and impacts that we were able to deduct from collected data (surveys, registration lists, social media and websites), the S4D4C

impact mailbox (impact@s4d4c.eu) as well as personal correspondences (personal emails and phone calls) with stakeholders. The presentation of activities is not exhaustive, instead we put forward those that best describe our contribution to reach the selected impacts.

3. Impact Highlights

Within the project's lifetime (January 2018 until April 2021) the team of S4D4C researchers and SD practitioners produced noticeable output (Annexes 1-8) that contributed to reaching the objectives mentioned above. The tangible impact is visible especially in the five areas described in the following subchapters.

3.1 Generating new knowledge and enriching the academic debate on Science Diplomacy

S4D4C partners produced a number of substantial scientific and policy-oriented publications. They are based on S4D4Cs research on a conceptual framework, the case studies and the governance framework. All in all, we can count 25 publications (20 publications on the S4DC website, 5 of which are policy briefs, and 5 publications in peer-reviewed journals; for a complete list, please refer to Annexes 1-3).

S4D4C has substantially contributed to evolving the academic debate of SD in two major ways: theoretically and empirically. In terms of advancing the theoretical debate, S4D4C has generated a number of key publications on the concept of SD (e.g. Rungius/Flink/Degelsegger-Marquez

2018; Flink/Rüffin 2019; Aukes/Kuhlmann 2019, Flink 2020; Rungius/Flink 2020). Most notably, Rungius and Flink have brought forth the first comprehensive reconstruction of the discourse of SD and its underlying narratives. Overall, S4D4C's academic contributions aimed at a high standard of methodological prudence and reflexivity.

S4D4C partners rejected using already-made definitions of SD. On this basis, the consortium produced a significant number of structured empirical investigations and insights. Beginning with a survey-based needs-assessment (Degelsegger-Marquez/Flink/Rungius 2019), the main focus of S4D4C's empirical efforts has been on nine SD case studies (Young/Flink/Dall 2020)

and their in-depth comparative analysis (Young et al 2020). Both empirical outputs are available on the S4D4C website⁴ and have been uploaded also to Research Gate.

The S4D4C project led the efforts to establish a thematic article collection on SD titled 'The past, present and future of European science diplomacy' in the Journal Humanities and Social Sciences Communications ISSN 2662-9992 (formerly Palgrave Communications) published by Nature. Three of the four editors are from S4D4C, as are a significant number of the advisory panel members. Nine articles have been approved, six published, and another still in the review process.

S4D4C partners have furthermore participated in more than 50 conferences and workshops (see Annex 6). The project has organized panels on SD at a number of major international events like at the conference of the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) in 2019 and 2020 as well as at the event of the International Public Policy Association in 2019 (ICPP). S4D4C contributed to the conference of the European Association for the Study

of Science and Technology (EASST/4S) in 2020, and the Canadian Science Policy Conference in 2020. For 2021, a panel at this year's EU-SPRI forum conference "in Oslo" is in preparation.

S4D4C researchers have presented a noticeable output that enriched the international SD debate as evidenced. A bibliometric analysis of the peer-reviewed articles showed us there are already some citations in the academic literature. Still, we need to be aware that there is a time lag between publication and citation that makes it difficult to rely on citation counts to be a meaningful measure of output. Download statistics from our S4D4C website, where all publications are presented, already now demonstrate the interest in the projects output (see Table 2).

4 For more information see: <https://www.s4d4c.eu/s4d4c-cases/>

Table 2: Download statistics from S4D4C website (most downloaded documents)

Publication	total	2021	2020	2019	2018
State-of-the-Art Report Published August 2018	2350	190	981	855	324
Romancing science for global solutions: on narratives and interpretative schemas of science diplomacy Published September 2020	1963 ⁵	1963	0	0	0
Science Diplomacy in the Making Published March 2020	2015	330	1685	0	0
Calling for a systemic change Published May 2020, updated March 2021	1926	116	1810	0	0
What it takes to do science diplomacy Published March 2019	1303	89	573	640	1
Science Diplomacy in the EU Published November 2018	687	47	227	318	95
Building Better Science Diplomacy for Global Challenges: insights from the COVID-19 crisis Published June 2020	597	58	539	0	0
The matters of science diplomacy Published September 2020	427	141	286	0	0
A New Protocol for Science Diplomacy Published February 2021	54	54	0	0	0

Source: S4D4C website statistics
(14.04.2021)

5 [Access counts retrieved from https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-020-00585-w](https://www.nature.com/articles/s41599-020-00585-w) (16.4.2021)

The authors also report an increased access to their older publications on SD which they assume is linked to their recent S4D4C related activities, like referring to them in our Online Course (see chapter 3.3). They were also increasingly invited to review SD papers for peer-reviewed journals (e.g. DZHW partners alone reviewed 15 papers since the beginning of S4D4C).

Although the impact of these activities still remains to be seen, several publications have generated some buzz on social networks, as is the case of the "New Science Diplomacy Protocol".

However, judging from individual responses received during workshops, practitioners have been inspired and intrigued by previous policy briefs of the consortium. Encouraging comments lauded the approach taken, one that does not focus on single actors but attempts to look at practices associated with SD instead. If this opinion is an indication of a more widespread demand, it could mean that S4D4C publications, like the "New Science Diplomacy Protocol", have a strong potential to remain popular in the future.

The Madrid Declaration (S4D4C 2019), one of S4D4Cs early outputs, emphasises the benefits SD can bring to tackling the global challenges of our time and outlines the principles needed to foster SD worldwide. It was signed by a group

of high-level experts. Soon after its publication, in early 2019, the Declaration reached the awareness of Ignazio Cassis, Foreign Minister of Switzerland. He published an article where he argues for the development and mainstreaming of SD and explains the term by referencing the Madrid Declaration. The Declaration has since been referenced many times by high-level officials.

In a final survey conducted by the S4D4C team in January and February 2021 we asked the question "Which of the following S4D4C activities and results are you aware of and how useful do you perceive them?" and subsequently listed our outputs. Although 18.9% of the respondents did indicate that they are not aware of the research publications, 55% valued them "useful" or "very useful". The same holds for policy reports, where 21% were not aware of these outputs, but 53.7% found them to be "useful" or very "useful".

S4D4Cs Final Networking event that took place in March 2021 (15th-19th) was one opportunity to display and promote the S4D4C outputs again to a wide and global audience. In the discussions at the diverse panels and sessions, strong interest in S4D4C outputs was expressed and we assume that perception and uptake of the scientific and policy-oriented outputs will rise and further influence the academic SD debate.

Focus: Visualisations of Science Diplomacy

S4D4C scientific and policy-oriented outputs are meant to be taken up by academia, policy makers and the interested public. They should also be helpful when creating training schemes. S4D4C thus invested some resources to create visual support. It helps to clarify the complexity of SD, provide recognizable highlights and reveal insights. One considerable example is the visualizations of the 12 principles of SD as defined in the "New Protocol for Science Diplomacy" (Aukes et al 2021). Another example is the infographic "Strengthening science diplomacy to tackle global challenges together – the case of the COVID-19 pandemic" (see Figure 3 in chapter 3.2).

3.2 Making practical knowledge on Science Diplomacy available

The S4D4C project aims to support the European SD community with the content, knowledge and skills necessary to successfully navigate the SD interface in Europe and beyond. To this end S4D4C organized a set of SD training programmes and provided training SD materials. Table 3 gives an overview of the main training activities and provides information on objectives, format, target groups and content (see Annex 5 for a complete list):

Table 3: Overview of S4D4C SD trainings

Training	Objectives	Training format	Target group and participants	Teaching design	Content
S4D4C Open Doors Programme (December 2018-April 2019).	Raise awareness of SD in the scientific community. Enhance networking with SD stakeholders and policy makers.	Series of consecutive meetings in different settings (Madrid, Brussels, London, Bonn, Berlin).	Early-career researchers from Europe interested in SD and related policy-making. Applications: 126 (plus 62 not eligible due to not targeted countries) Participants: 5	Networking events. Field trips to embassies and other SD bodies (research ministry, research funding agencies, European Space Agency). Workshops. Participation in SD events (as speakers).	SD concepts. Career Development. Skills. Exchange on mode of operation in SD with diplomats.

Training	Objectives	Training format	Target group and participants	Teaching design	Content
S4D4C workshops in Trieste (August 2019) and Vienna (November 2019)	Understand the state-of-the-art of SD in Europe. Convey SD skills to work in the field.	3-day in-person trainings.	Adequate mix of early, mid and senior career scientists and diplomats. Applications: 400 (Trieste, 300 were not eligible due to not targeted countries) and 200 (Vienna, 110 were not eligible due to not targeted countries). Participants: 25 (for each training).	Theoretical and case study related input. Simulation exercises. Group work. Networking. Visit to an international research facility. Social activities.	Science Communication. International science system. Negotiation skills. Case Studies: Water Diplomacy, Open Science and Global Health. Career Development.
S4D4C European Science Diplomacy Online Course (started June 2020)	Meet the growing demand. Raise awareness and improve understanding of SD. Share results of case study research and conceptual work.	15-hour online training as a Massive Open Online Course (MOOC). Free of charge. Registered users manage their own time. Completion of the course is rewarded by an S4D4C official certificate.	Professionals with an interest in SD and a diplomatic or scientific background: career diplomats, embassy staff, counsellors/attachés, career scientists, policymakers, graduate and undergraduate students. Participants: Some 6000 registered users from all over the world. 600 certificates issued.	Readings. Recorded video interviews of experts. Self-assessment and quizzes.	SD conceptual frameworks. SD stakeholders and networks. European Union approach to SD. National, regional, and thematic SD approaches. Required skills to operate in SD. Overview of some S4D4C and InsSciDE empirical case studies.

Training	Objectives	Training format	Target group and participants	Teaching design	Content
S4D4C interactive webinar series (October – December 2020)	<p>Foster interaction and networking.</p> <p>Provide opportunities for engagement as spin-off to the online course.</p> <p>Discuss questions about online modules.</p>	Series of six interactive 2-hour webinars.	<p>Registered users having completed S4D4C European SD Online Course and prospective users.</p> <p>Applications: ca. 650 (per webinar)</p> <p>Participants: 160 from all over the world.</p>	<p>Panel discussion.</p> <p>Interactive chat.</p> <p>Break-out sessions.</p> <p>Instant surveys.</p>	Same as in the online course above.

Source: Own compilation

The two SD workshops in Vienna and Trieste as well as the Open Doors scheme were evaluated in retrospect through questionnaires. We can sum up that they were perceived as very satisfying and helpful for the participants. With regard to participants' learning and take-away impressions, which is of importance for the impact of the training schemes, participants ranked the variety of the topics presented as well as the quality of the speakers very positively. A majority assessed that their skills⁶ and knowledge⁷ on SD had changed a lot or to a very large extent due to the trainings, which indicates an impact on the trainee's skills and behaviour in future SD involvements.

We would like to highlight the Online Course on European SD, which was welcomed by the community. The pace of early registrations surpassed the team's expectations: only 3 weeks after its launch, 3000 registrations

were counted and at the end of the project (April 2021) more than 6000 persons have registered and 600 certificates were issued. This was clearly possible because the course is open and free of charge, and probably also because of the timing of its start: We launched it quite at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, which fostered a rising interest for offers of online-trainings altogether.

The results of the satisfactory survey for the online course clearly revealed that most participants did not know anything about SD before starting the course, or only a little. The learning curve rose sharply with the material provided in the eight modules of the online course. Most of the 1227 respondents were confident about the use of their newly acquired knowledge and found the course useful for their own personal career objectives.

6 Trieste Workshop: 77,8 % of participants, N=18. Internal Evaluation, not published.

7 Vienna Workshop: 60 % of participants, N=20. Internal Evaluation, not published.

Figure 1: Extract from Satisfactory Survey update of the Online Course for European Science Diplomacy (April 2021)

Questions regarding the event

Respondents' sentiments on five-point Likert scale

Source: Satisfaction survey (April 2021), N= 1227. Internal evaluation, not published.

Specifically, all four sections related to the different contents of the course received similar positive assessments: Q1: "[...] thematic and regional approaches of SD?" (average score 3.65), Q2: "Have you gained insights into European Science Diplomacy?" (average score 3.67), Q8: "[...] stakeholders and networks of SD?" (average 3.73), Q6: "[...] skills of science diplomats?" (average 3.79).

Most respondents were confident about the use of their newly acquired knowledge, as can be seen in replies to question 9 (predominant answers average/a lot, average score 3.53). As regards the benefit for their own career options, a majority found the course moderately to positively useful (see question 7 with a majority of answers being average/a lot, average score 3.69).

The replies to question 3 ("Have your expectations been met?") in contrast were very positive (average score 3,9). Also, the mix of material used in the online course (video, literature, references) was generally perceived in a very positive way (question 10, average score 4.18). Question 11 confirms this trend: a large majority would recommend this course to a colleague (average score 4.13).

This demonstrates that our trainings activities really did make a difference in terms of the transfer of theoretical knowledge of SD into practice within the stakeholder community.

Over time, the online course was also endorsed by different organisations, which we assess as an indicator of its impact potential in raising competences in SD. The European External Action Service (EEAS)⁸ promoted it in its internal Learning & Development Weekly Update and the Belgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs included the course in its digital library⁹. It was also promoted by the Panama Ministry of Foreign Affairs (see also chapter 3.4) and the Latin American

Science Diplomacy organisation DiploCientifica translated part of the online course to Spanish on their website¹⁰. The University of Trieste even plans to include parts of the online course among the training options for their students to get awarded additional ECTS credits¹¹. The Humboldt University will use the course in the upcoming summer semester as part of the MA study program Social Studies of Science, module 'Governance of Science'. We do count this as a success and think it will lead to a systemic impact in the long run.

The interactive webinar series was a task not originally foreseen when the project was designed. But an interim evaluation of the Satisfactory Survey of the Online Course from August 2020 clearly showed us that students missed interaction amongst each other and with the authors of the online course. As a result, the webinar series was designed and implemented from September to December 2020 as a complementary learning environment for SD and six webinars that corresponded to the modules of the online course were designed (for further information see Annex 6).

The aims were to design a deeper knowledge transfer, to provide networking and community-building opportunities and also to support mutual understanding between stakeholders. In order to achieve these objectives, very interactive formats such as breakout rooms, quizzes, surveys and even simulation games were designed for the sessions. As it was a new and quite ad-hoc initiative, no systematic evaluation was carried out. The feedback we received via chat, email and social media was very positive though, many participants followed all six sessions. Participants expressed their gratitude for the webinars and the learning experience. Discussions and questions were very vivid throughout the events and contact information were exchanged.

8 Source: Email from EEAS to S4D4C on 26th October 2020.

9 Source: Email from an employee of the Belgian Foreign Affairs Office on 20th August 2020 to S4D4C.

10 See: <https://diplomaciacentifica.org/que-es-la-diplomacia-cientifica/>

11 Source: Email from University of Trieste on 15th April 2021

Figure 2: Tweet about Interactive webinar No 6 "Hands on! Science Diplomacy in Action"

Source: Twitter

As part of the endeavour to provide good quality SD training and resources, S4D4C developed a wide range of educational materials in the context of its trainings (see also Annex 4). In order to secure maximum uptake, they are distributed with a CC-BY or CC-BY-NC open source license and provided without fee on the project's website in the section "Training Materials" .

Focus: S4D4C open source materials for maximum impact

S4D4C dedicated a whole deliverable to guiding trainers and institutions when designing and executing SD trainings: The "Toolkit for Trainers" (Josten et al 2020). The information and recommendations provided in the toolkit are based mainly on the training experiences gained within the S4D4C project. This means we not only allow, but also foster and support any use and recomposition of the content in order to achieve sustainability and boost quality and standards of SD trainings.

One example is the infographic we developed which was used in several webinars and presentations, also outside of the S4D4C context, and perceived as very helpful and supportive for the understanding of SD interfaces and processes (as was expressed in personal feedback by users).

Figure 3: Infographic "Strengthening science diplomacy to tackle global challenges together – the case of the COVID-19 pandemic"

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 770342.

Source: S4D4C website

3.3 Raising a global Science Diplomacy Community

S4D4D was funded with the purpose of focusing on European SD, its shapes, dimensions and stakeholders as well as its position in the global stakeholder landscape. Reaching out to the global community was foreseen from the start with the inclusion of international associated partners (among them international organisations and partners in the US, Russia, India and Japan). While it was foreseen to be an explicit task when the project started, it further gained momentum during the implementation.

S4D4C organized three European (2018, 2019, 2021) and two global (2018 and 2021) stakeholder events. Especially the

Final Networking Event that was massively endorsed on twitter #SciDipNet2021 is a true success story: it involved 122 speakers and 765 attendees from all over the world.

The Madrid Declaration on Science Diplomacy (S4D4C 2019) was published quickly after the 1st Networking Event (Madrid) as one of the conference's results. In February 2019, right after its announcement, 44 high-level experts had signed it. Over time the Madrid Declaration attracted quite some interest (see also chapter 3.1) and by April 2021 167 individuals from Africa, Asia, Australia/Oceania, Europe as well as North and South America have signed it.

Figure 4: Enrolment in S4D4C interactive webinar series (registrations, participant's country of origin)

Source: DLR (2020) based on registration statistics of the interactive webinar series

The Online Course on European SD and the interactive webinar series (see also chapter 3.2) meant a great leap forward in terms of global outreach and diversified target groups: they attracted an audience from 97 countries over the world (see Figure 4).

From those 20 countries with the highest enrolment rate, 11 were non-European countries (including the United Kingdom).

Not only geographical range, but also addressing multiple stakeholder groups was a concern as we aimed to design our activities to be inclusive. The analysis of the Satisfaction Survey of the online course in April 2021 shows that we reached a wide range of target groups (see Figure 5): Most common scientific backgrounds were social sciences (top answer, 27% of all participants), closely followed by natural sciences (26 %) and medical and health science (20)¹². Apparently, individuals from different disciplines considered the trainings as valuable for them. As to the professional background, the results clearly indicate that most participants were scientists (almost half of all respondents, 1227 in total), as well as others (students). A small number of the

scientists that took part in the survey specified to have some diplomatic responsibilities (5,4%), the majority did not (39,2%). In total, 6% of respondents were diplomats, 2,9% of those had a scientific background, the others did not. The reasons for the relatively low participation rate of diplomats might be diverse: is it due to training content, to marketing and outreach, to career or intellectual incentives, and also to the actual distribution of different professions? Within the S4D4C team the topic was intensely discussed, and is an area where further research is needed.

Figure 5: Target Groups of European Online Course (in %)

¹² In some cases, participants chose more than one option. In those cases, only the first one was taken into account.

Focus: Reaching out to Down Under

S4D4C partners made sure that outreach included Oceania (Figure 6): they participated in the European Research Days 2020 (#ERD2020) Australia & New Zealand edition. The special session of the last day of the event, that took place from 25 to the 27 November 2020 was hosted by S4D4C. In the panel, several facets of SD were discussed.

Impact can also be demonstrated by stakeholders actively getting in touch with us and looking for partnerships or inviting S4D4C partners to participate in their SD related events: A member of the Turkish Academic and Scientific Cooperation Portal of Turkey (TABIP) inquired about possible collaboration and partnership options with S4D4C under the scope of bilateral agreements. Cooperation with Indian stakeholders was good from the beginning, as shown in the interview with S4D4C's Stakeholder's Voice#3 (see Annex 7) and cooperation with Indian stakeholders

remained vibrant throughout the project. In March 2021, S4D4C partners together with colleagues from the sister project InSciDE placed an article on the topic of SD trainings for global challenges in the *Indian Science and Diplomacy Review*¹³.

Another important aspect of S4D4C outreach was the creation and support of networks and large-scale alliances in and around SD.

The AUF (agence universitaire de la francophonie) has set up a task force on SD,

13 Article with the title „A New Generation of Trainings on Science Diplomacy for Global Challenges: Insights from two European Projects" was accepted on 23 March 2021. The issue of the journal was not yet published when this report was finalised.

in order to develop its own SD approach and tools for its members, and to connect with other international university associations committed to highlighting the role of universities and higher education in SD. S4D4C partner University of Lille as well as University of le Havre from the sister project InsSiDE have been involved in this task force from the start, feeding the discussion with the outputs of the two EU projects, and supporting and advising the AUF in this initiative substantially.

In December 2020 for example, a joint workshop was co-organized by S4D4C with the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM) to

explore the role of SD in the Mediterranean. Participants, amongst them stakeholders from the Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Region (PRIMA), the AUF and the SESAME Synchrotron in Jordan, worked on policy recommendations on how to foster a joint SD strategy between major actors in the region.

With the launch of the "EU Science Diplomacy Alliance for Addressing Global Challenges" at the closing ceremony of the S4D4C final networking event, an important step on the road to an institutionalisation of European SD was taken.

Figure 6: EU Science Diplomacy Alliance for Addressing Global Challenges - logo (draft) and founding members

Source: S4D4C Website

The nucleus of this network is based on partner organisations of the three EU funded SD projects S4D4C, InsSciDE and EI-CSID.¹⁴ As the research consortia of the three projects focused on different aspects of SD, a broad and complementary approach is assured.

The EU SD Alliance is set up with the aim to facilitate interactions and dialogue, training, institutional capacity building and coordination of grant-seeking or use of joint funding, if available. It is designed as a space for cooperative activities and voluntary coordination, and relies upon the participating membership community and

networks to highlight and select different areas and innovative activities to be pursued. It is hoped that a great variety of societal challenges may be addressed over time and sustainable and fruitful interaction with partners outside of Europe can be pursued.

3.4 Shaping national and regional Science Diplomacy policies

National and regional SD discussions have strongly benefitted from S4D4C inputs. This started in 2018 in Austria, Germany and Spain. For the case of Germany, for example, discussions have deepened immensely in 2019 and found its peak in 2020 and 2021. Tim Flink (DZHW) drafted and presented two input papers to the Federal Foreign Offices working group on SD in 2019, on how to reform ministerial and inter-organisational coordination mechanisms of German SD, how to better integrate scientific advice and how to foster in-house trainings.

The German partners in S4D4C (DLR) have close links to government officials in the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). Their participation in the project initiated an exchange on the topic that went beyond selective discussions. The BMBF,

who has been Germany's SD player for many years, took an interest in the project's work and supported it in multiple ways, such as, by organising a get-together event during the 2nd networking event in Berlin (2019) and participation of BMBF officials in two of the three projects' networking events (Keynote of Fritjhof Maennel during 2nd networking event in Berlin and video message of Anja Karliczek, Federal Minister of Education and Research, at the Final Networking Meeting in March 2021). Fritjhof Maennel additionally took an active part in one of the interactive webinars in November 2020 and gave insight to BMBF's education and science diplomacy approach.

Impact of S4D4C work became apparent as discussions with the BMBF on the topic enriched the discussion within the ministry.

14 More information about the three projects is provided here: www.science-diplomacy.eu.

With the support of S4D4C partner DLR, the BMBF deepened its understanding of science and education policy by indentifying three main pillars: Connect, Inform and Enable. The Federal Minister endorsed this approach and with the support of the DLR the model was made public through a website offering an award for outstanding SD research projects ("Raising the profile of education and science diplomacy") and co-organising (in cooperation with the Federal Ministry of Foreign Affairs) an SD related event during the Berlin Science Week in 2020 during the German EU Council Presidency (only to name a few).

exchange with DLR Project Management Agency on Science Diplomacy was very fruitful. Their close connection to the S4D4C project enriched the discussion with up-to-date research findings and we had the chance to participate actively in some of S4D4Cs events.^{15"}

This strategic approach generated momentum and BMBF is further advancing it: Within the G7 science and technology ministers` meeting in 2020 BMBF initiated the uptake of science diplomacy in the Declaration on COVID-19 (G7/8 Science and Technology Ministers, 2020).

One BMBF official assessed the S4D4C contribution as follows: "The conceptional

Figure 7: Landing page of German SD award "Raising the profile of education and Science Diplomacy"

Focus: S4D4C's influence on national policies – the Austrian example

3 Questions – 3 Answers: An interview with Martina Hartl, Austrian Ministry of Education, Science and Research

Question 1: You were involved in some of S4D4Cs activities (Networking Event, interviews for Online Course etc.). How would you describe the exchange with the project?

The exchange was very fruitful, not only from a content point of view but also for getting to know experts in the field that we could connect to in our further work on national level.

Question 2: Did the interaction lead to new national initiatives on SD?

In Austria, it has led to the launch of a study of SD actors in Austria with the aim to facilitate national networking, EU alignment and the creation of a long-term SD Roundtable format.

Question 3: Would you support the assessment that S4D4C had an impact on the Austrian (or Ministry of Education, Science and Research's) science diplomacy discussion?

Through the project, SD has received additional attention and the explicit and implicit role of the Education and Science Ministry is now being reflected more closely, also in cooperation with the Foreign Ministry.

S4D4C has also had an impact on regional SD approaches: most tangible is the Latin American example.

Building on previous cooperation of several S4D4C partners in international cooperation dialogues and research projects with the region the cooperation flourished in the SD context. We counted a large number of participations in events and exchanges with Latin American partners, only a selection is described in the following.

S4D4C Partners Ana Elorza (FECYT) and Marga Gual Soler supported National Council of Science and Technology of Panama (SENACYT) and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Panama to elaborate their SD Strategy in 2019 (Panama Ministry of Foreign Affairs 2019). This was a follow-up of an event in Bolivia in 2017, where first contacts between FECYT and Panaman officials had been established. Furthermore, Open-Doors grantee Marta Pulido participated in a webinar on the topic of the current state and future challenges of Panama's SD strategy, which was also organized by SENACYT in collaboration with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the City of Knowledge Foundation, where she introduced the S4D4C Online Course on European SD (see chapter 3.3). The Panama Ministry of Foreign Affairs subsequently joined in promoting and sharing the S4D4C's open online course .

In Colombia, thanks to S4DC4 activities and networking, a series of events and spaces have taken place since 2019. For example, the University Externado of Colombia hosted a webinar that was initiated by S4D4C member Gonzalo Ordóñez-Matamoros (UT), to discuss different viewpoints on international experiences and a space for reflection considering the country's context in SD on 16 July 2020 (see Annex 6 for details). Participating panellists ranged from researchers to government officials from the Colombian Ministry of Foreign Affairs. It became apparent, that the ministry had not yet incorporated SD as a strategy for Colombia's foreign policy. However, important steps in creating the necessary institutional conditions for the development of

SD are under way. Information from the event was also used in an article published at El Tiempo, one of the key newspapers of the country . A task force with members from the Colombian scientific and diplomatic communities was created on 30th October 2020, to meet periodically to discuss and promote the interaction between science and diplomacy through joint dissemination events and training initiatives. Members come from the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, the Diplomatic Academy of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and several Colombian universities and research centres. The task force also serves as an advisory group to the Colombian Ministry of STI for the development of a national Science Diplomacy strategy.

In November 2020, S4D4C-partners Susanne Keppler-Schlesinger (DA) and Lorenzo Melchor (FECYT) were invited by the Diplomatic Service of Peru to partake in a webinar with the title "Science Diplomacy and Peru's Foreign Policy". The event aimed at understanding SD, its practical applications and to provoke a more in-depth discussion and reflection about the impact and policy challenges it poses to developing countries like Peru. Also, the importance of assessing those challenges, in particular in respect of its foreign policy. The webinar and wider work of S4D4C was welcomed by participants, as indicated by comments on Twitter.

One of our team members, Marga Gual Soler, authored a report for the UNESCO Regional Office for Science for Latin America and the Caribbean. The UNESCO policy paper "Science Diplomacy in Latin America and the Caribbean: Strategies, Mechanisms, and Perspectives" is the first comprehensive analysis of the science, technology, and innovation diplomacy landscape in the Latin American region. It will have an uptake in the Latin American regional discussion on SD as it was conducted as part of the preparatory activities for the Latin American Open Science Forum (Foro CILAC) to be held April 2021 in Buenos Aires, Argentina. Inviting S4D4C partners to these high-level

discussions is something we recognize as important in the conceptual and analytical discussion and we assume that our input will contribute and have an impact on the further development of the field in Latin America. Feedback from stakeholders of the DiploCientifica does support this point of view.

Another impact of S4D4Cs interaction with Latin American countries is displayed in the large involvement of Latin American individuals in our activities, such as the networking events, the online course and interactive webinar series (as described in chapter 3.3).

S4D4C partners also had intensive exchanges with North American scholars and practitioners as well as some activities in Asia, which we will not detail here. The Latin American example illustrates what the S4D4C project was able to accomplish in terms of regional impact.

3.5 Advancing European Science Diplomacy

Preparation for European SD for better a profile and stronger identity has been one of S4D4Cs main objectives. Our activities were accordingly geared towards important European stakeholders on a personal and institutional level. Relevant outreach activities were part of our work from the beginning, which led to a sustainable cooperation over time.

S4D4C partners from ZSI and FECYT thus actively participated in the Task Force on SD of the Strategic Forum for International S&T Cooperation (SFIC). ZSI was invited as an S4D4C partner to some of the Task Force's meetings (upon request), FECYT was nominated by Spain to partake in the Task Force. Both partners thus supported the framing of a common strategic approach in order to strengthen the impact of SD within the European Research Area and Horizon

Europe. Support included substantial inputs to the

- Input Paper „ Advancing the impact of Science Diplomacy at EU and Member States level through targeted support and improved coordination" (March 2020)
- Working Paper "Anchoring science diplomacy in Horizon Europe developing specific subjects and activities" (September 2020)
- SFIC Science Diplomacy Survey (currently ongoing)

Figure 8: SFIC Task Force on Science Diplomacy Working Paper (Screenshot)

SFIC TASK FORCE ON SCIENCE DIPLOMACY WORKING PAPER
“ANCHORING SCIENCE DIPLOMACY IN HORIZON EUROPE -
DEVELOPING SPECIFIC SUBJECTS AND ACTIVITIES”

RATIONALE:

This document complements the information of the Strategic Forum for International S&T Cooperation (SFIC) input paper adopted on “Advancing the impact of Science Diplomacy at EU and Member States level through targeted support and improved coordination” which describes strategic activities to be considered with view to strengthening the anchoring and impact of Science Diplomacy (SD) within the European Research Area and Horizon Europe to (ERAC-SFIC 1352/20).

The aim of this paper revision is to support a brainstorming exercise for specifically developing Science Diplomacy aspects of Horizon Europe, acknowledging that Horizon Europe itself is a Science Diplomacy tool through offering an open, transparent and globally relevant programme, which benefits go beyond the EU.

These ideas should not be seen as detailed descriptions of call topics but as an illustration of topics currently discussed in the Science Diplomacy Community as well as in connection with the EU Commission priorities such as the Green Deal, Climate, Digitisation, Health and Security. Hence, the ideas here proposed should be seen as an inspiration on how to further strengthen the diffusion of Science Diplomacy approaches and impacts in Horizon Europe.

Source: <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-1357-2020-INIT/en/pdf>

Page 2 of the Working Paper quotes (SFIC 2020): "The work of this paper has been a collaborative effort with Science Diplomacy experts engaged in different EU and international projects and activities and we would especially like to acknowledge the extensive contributions of the S4D4C as well as INSSCIDE projects and their coordinators Ms. Elke Dall and Ms. Claire Mays to this paper".

These documents in turn also influenced the planning of the first Work Programmes in Horizon Europe.

In addition, close contact was established with key stakeholders in the EC such as the Directorate for International Cooperation and the responsible policy officers for science diplomacy or the members of cabinet responsible for SD.

Focus: Commissioner Mariya Gabriel endorses S4D4C and emphasizes the role of SD

As a highlight, Mariya Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture Education and Youth provided some insight into the SD of the European Union by publishing a statement on S4D4C’s website (see Annex 7) in October 2020 and also tweeted about it¹⁶.

She also participated in S4D4C's Final Networking Event in March 2021 by contributing a recorded message.

Another development is that a "Science Diplomacy Booster" pilot has been included in the Management Plan 2021 of DG Research and Innovation of the EC¹⁷, where science counsellors and R&I correspondents will jointly organize outreach activities. This lies in line with recommendations expressed by S4D4C and SFIC.

16 see: <https://twitter.com/gabrielmariya/status/1321858009488916482?s=12>

17 see: https://ec.europa.eu/info/system/files/management-plan-rtd-2021_en.pdf, p. 18

From the beginning, cooperation with the EEAS was one of the major interests of the project, having in mind the objective to support European SD vis-à-vis third countries. The new Science & Technology Advisor at the European External Action Service was appointed (Jan-Marco Müller). S4D4C had already collaborated with him in his former position as Head of the Directorate Office of the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) (for example, he was involved in the 1st Networking Event in Madrid and an interview Partner in Stakeholder's Voices #1, see Annex 7) and the fruitful exchange deepened in his new position. He participated in one edition of the interactive webinar series and, along with his EEAS colleagues Suvi Seppäläinen, Advisor on Transatlantic Relations, Emerging Technologies, and Foresight, Strategic Policy Planning Team, and Kristin de Peyron, Deputy Managing Director Human Rights, Global and Multilateral Affairs, played an

active role in S4D4Cs Final Networking event. In March 2021, the event was mentioned in the section "Learning Suggestions" in the update of a dedicated EEAS newsletter (as was our online course, see chapter 3.2). Both endorsements are valuable proof of acknowledgement of S4D4C activities in the EEAS and are an important step towards one target group we envisioned for the course and the event.

EEAS and EC expressed credible interest in the European Alliance on SD, which is currently in the making (see chapter 3.4). We believe that a further interaction between the Alliance and EEAS and ED will lead to a deepened and strategic approach to European SD.

Conclusions

S4D4C received funding from the European Commission in order to follow its objectives as were laid out in the project proposal. Long-term impact was addressed and linked to the multiple project activities.

The project work was successfully carried out as planned, with some activities and outputs being added as a reaction to unanticipated circumstances (e.g. COVID-19 related policy paper and interactive webinar series).

S4D4C had certain impacts in a couple of areas:

Its research and researchers' engagement in conferences did generate insights and enriched the academic and practitioner's debate on SD. Analyses and discussions have already been acknowledged in the scientific community and proved to be of value. We expect that the uptake and citations will rise in the following months and will in the long-run lead to a better contribution of SD to EU and foreign policy.

Training activities carried out by the project team made practical knowledge on SD available to a wide range of target groups, as well thematically as geographically. Trainings showed to be successful in terms of learning experience and transfer of knowledge. In the long run, capable European science diplomats will contribute to a stronger EU position in the global context. Although outreach addressed scientists as well as diplomats, we would have liked to engage more diplomats than we did, especially in the online training. It will be a task for the European Union Science Diplomacy Alliance to address this as a challenge and dedicate further efforts to it.

S4D4C outreach activities, conferences and trainings led to the gentle formation of an SD community, not only in the European but global SD context and throughout various stakeholder groups. It furthermore supported existing networks and alliances and is a founding force in the new European Alliance on Science Diplomacy. The latter aims to be the space to escort and bundle EU SD developments.

By interacting with national and European government officials, S4D4C partners supported the shaping of national and regional SD policies in a number of cases. The further strategic development of national SD within a European context does already support enhanced cooperation between EU and its MS as well as international partners at the interface of science and international policy.

European science policy had already been well coordinated amongst MS. The strategic development of SD as a tool of the EUs own foreign policy is still in the making. By establishing good contacts to the relevant institutions, S4D4C contributed to this task. Research outputs and policy-oriented recommendations were acknowledged by government officials on several occasions already and we are hopeful that this will continue in the near future. We believe our work will have a positive impact on the EU's SD approach and the pathway to increased inclusivity and improved global responses to societal challenges.

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Annex 1: Outputs of the analytical and conceptual work

[The New Protocol for Science Diplomacy](#)

Science Diplomacy has the potential to play a considerable role in future international collaborations intent on tackling societal challenges. This ambition cannot be achieved by positioning science diplomacy as a soft power to be utilized by single countries to further their interests. Tackling societal challenges is a cosmopolitan ambition and common, shared interest that requires collective action. The actions required need to be organized by the domain of science, technology and innovation in close collaboration with foreign policymakers.

[Romancing science for global solutions](#)

One of S4D4C's mission is to increase the conceptual understanding of science diplomacy addressing global challenges. This also includes a critical review of how the concept is currently used to better understand and use it. ...

[Critical perspective on Science Diplomacy in The Hague Journal of Diplomacy](#)

S4D4C team member Tim Flink published an article entitled "The sensationalist Discourse of Science Diplomacy: A critical reflection". This piece is part of the series of special articles that S4D4C researchers have contributed to The ...

[Elucidating what a science diplomat is](#)

S4D4C welcomes the recent publication in Open Access of the article entitled "What Is a Science Diplomat?" and written by our S4D4C partner Lorenzo Melchor. This piece is part of the series of special articles ...

[S4D4C research on science diplomacy reflected in articles in "Forschung: Politik-Strategie-Management"](#)

S4D4C partners Ewert Aukes, Stefan Kuhlmann and Tim Flink are proud to announce that two of their recent articles have now been published in the current edition of the journal "Forschung: Politik – Strategie – ...

[What it takes to do science diplomacy. Baseline analysis and needs assessment](#)

One of the principal objectives of the S4D4C project is to increase the capacities of EU and EU Member State science diplomats and to offer relevant knowledge resources and training opportunities that support their work. ...

[S4D4C's State-of-the-Art Report on Science Diplomacy](#)

One of the goals of our early project work in S4D4C is to provide the conceptual grounds for our subsequent analyses of science diplomacy cases and governance. As one element of this, DZHW colleagues Charlotte ...

Annex 2: Policy outputs

[Policy Brief: Why science diplomacy needs evaluative backing](#)

In this new policy brief, S4D4C team member Tim Flink presents a first set of guiding ideas that can be used by policy actors to evaluate science diplomacy strategies. Science diplomacy has been a rather ...

[Policy Brief: A New Protocol for Science Diplomacy](#)

In this policy brief, S4D4C team members Ewert Aukes, Stefan Kuhlmann, James Wilsdon and Gonzalo Ordonez-Matamoros introduce the New Protocol for Science Diplomacy which is displayed on our website here. The policy brief is ...

[Policy Brief: Building Better Science Diplomacy for Global Challenges: insights from the COVID-19 crisis](#)

In this new policy brief, Mitchell Young and a team of contributors from S4D4C elaborate on what we can learn from the COVID-19 crisis to build a stronger science diplomacy interface for better handling global ...

[Calling for a systemic change: Towards a EU science diplomacy for addressing global challenges](#)

We have witnessed how COVID-19 has brought to the limit health, social, economic, and labour systems and provoked huge turbulences in multilateral relations. In parallel, science and its ability to inform policies for better response ...

[S4D4C policy brief: Towards effective science diplomacy practice](#)

Our S4D4C colleagues from the University of Twente, Ewert Aukes, Gonzalo Ordóñez-Matamoros, Stefan Kuhlman, and Sanaz Honarmand-Ebrahimi have published another policy brief focusing on key premises for the development of effective governance mechanisms for science ...

[Policy brief on science diplomacy in the European Union](#)

Tim Flink and Charlotte Rungius, our S4D4C colleagues at DZHW/Germany, have published our project's first policy brief focusing on practices and prospects in European Union science diplomacy. With the European Commission making greater efforts in engaging ...

[Two years since the 1st S4D4C Networking Meeting in Madrid / Madrid Declaration](#)

On the 14th of December 2020, S4D4C celebrates the second anniversary since we organised the 1st S4D4C Networking Meeting, which took place on the 12-14th December 2018 in Madrid (Spain). S4D4C had been running for ...

Annex 3: Case studies

[The 'Matters' of Science Diplomacy: Transversal Analysis of the S4D4C Case Studies](#)

What matters in science diplomacy? That is the question that our new publication "The 'Matters' of Science Diplomacy: Transversal Analysis of the S4D4C Case Studies" aims to answer. To do so, the transversal analysis critically ...

[Science Diplomacy in the Making: Case-based insights from the S4D4C project](#)

We are very happy to announce that the next major outcome of the S4D4C project is now available online – Science Diplomacy in the Making: Case-based insights from the S4D4C project – is a volume ...

[Science diplomacy and infectious diseases: Between national and European narratives](#)

The Zika epidemics in 2015 and 2016 provided a platform for further elaboration of science diplomacy used by the EU institutions and EU Member States. The response was characterised by an interplay between the political, diplomatic, medical and scientific communities performed within national, European, and global frameworks.

[Water diplomacy and its future in the national, regional and European environments](#)

Water diplomacy represents a challenge for bringing the worlds of diplomacy and science closer together; it has the potential to shape the diplomatic environment as well as to create new interfaces, techniques, and team strategies in science and foreign policy.

Cyber security: Mapping the role of science diplomacy in the cyber field

Cyber security has entered the agenda of the international community and has quickly been transformed from a purely technical topic to an issue of diplomacy. The term 'cyber diplomacy' has come into global use, and countries are keenly deploying their own 'cyber diplomats'.

The science and diplomacy of global challenges: Food security in EU-Africa relations

Over the past 20 years, a set of institutions, concerns, competencies, partnerships, and programmes have shaped the features of EU-African Union food security diplomacy. To what extent has science played a role in deploying this food security diplomacy?

International dimensions of the EU's FET Flagships: Large-scale strategic research investments as a site of de-facto science diplomacy

A study of Future and Emerging Technology (FET) Flagship initiatives as potential mechanisms of EU science diplomacy reveals that their governance models and design as research policy instruments have sectoral foreign policy dynamics.

Open Science Diplomacy

Following the call for 'open science, open innovation, and open to the world' by the EU Commissioner for Research, Science and Innovation Carlos Moedas in 2015, we look for applications and implications of open science in science diplomacy.

SESAME – An international research infrastructure in the Middle East

SESAME is a synchrotron light source user's facility in the Middle East. The international research centre was initiated with the explicit intention to foster scientific cooperation among a number of countries that share a history of conflict.

Joint international research programming as a case of science diplomacy

Joint international research programming is a common but underrated case of science diplomacy. It engages funding agencies as intermediary organisations that are compelled to cooperate at the intersection of science policy and international affairs.

Science advice in the European Union: Crafting collective understanding of transnational issues

In thinking about science diplomacy, it is important to not only acknowledge the formal structures for science diplomacy, but also to consider the ways in which internal capacities for science diplomacy might already be built into diplomatic systems.

Annex 4: Training outputs

[Teaching Science Diplomacy: Toolkit for trainers](#)

Are you setting up a training exercise on science diplomacy? Looking for inspiration and guidance? As the demand for capacity-building at the science diplomacy interface grows around the world, this new toolkit for trainers helps ...

[Building a Science Diplomacy Curriculum](#)

Our colleague Marga Gual Soler (TWAS) co-authored an article with Jean-Christophe Mauduit, Department of Science, Technology, Engineering and Public Policy, University College London, London, United Kingdom in "Frontiers in Education" titled "Building a Science Diplomacy ...

[Training Materials on Science Diplomacy](#)

In 2019, S4D4C organised two training workshops on Science Diplomacy – one in October in Trieste and one in November in Vienna. Since then, we have been working on preparing the training materials used during ...

[Online Knowledge Resources Platform for Science Diplomacy](#)

We are very proud to announce that our Online Knowledge Resources Platform for Science Diplomacy is now available as part of the S4D4C website! Our aim for this platform is to offer a collection of ...

[Open Doors Programme](#)

In November 2018, the S4D4C project "Science for/in diplomacy for addressing global challenges" published its 1st call for the "Open Door Programme" attracting applications from scientists working in various research fields and with an interest ...

Annex 5: S4D4C networking and training events

[S4D4C Interactive Webinar Series 6 Hands on! Science Diplomacy in Action: Review](#)

Our last interactive webinar on our online course took place on the 17th of December 2020. Practical examples of science diplomacy are key to the understanding of what science diplomacy is. A mixed team of ...

S4D4C Interactive Webinar Series 5 Science Diplomacy Skills: Roundtable and Interactive Exercise

The 5th S4D4C Webinar took place on the 3rd December 2020. It was based on Module 6 of the S4D4C European Science Diplomacy online course on Science Diplomacy Skills. The practice of science diplomacy encompasses a ...

S4D4C Interactive Webinar Series 4 What Are National and Regional Approaches of Science Diplomacy?

One way to identify national (or regional) approaches to science diplomacy (SD) is to scrutinize documents from national and international diplomatic contexts in which diplomacy meets science and vice versa. You may find policy guidelines ...

S4D4C Interactive Webinar Series 3 What are the EU practices in Science Diplomacy?

In the last years, the European Commission has strongly embraced science diplomacy as a fundamental tool of external relations and as a means to leverage the impact of European research and innovation framework programmes. Although ...

S4D4C Interactive Webinar Series 2 Who Are the Science Diplomacy Stakeholders?

The second episode of our interactive webinar focused on deepening students' understanding of module 3: Who Are the Science Diplomacy Stakeholders? The webinar offered an interactive learning experience combining discussions between experts on the content ...

S4D4C Interactive Webinar Series 1 What Is Science Diplomacy?

The first episode of our interactive webinar focused on deepening students' understanding of module 2: What is Science Diplomacy? The webinar offered an interactive learning experience combining discussions between experts on the content of the ...

S4D4C workshop in Vienna Opening Science! Opening Diplomacy!

From November 25-27, Vienna was a melting pot for science diplomacy practitioners from around the globe. Not only that the S4D4C consortium organised its second workshop on science diplomacy at the Diplomatic Academy (DA) of ...

[S4D4C workshop in Trieste: Looking at the future of European Science Diplomacy](#)

The S4D4C consortium has recently concluded the first workshop on science diplomacy in Trieste, Italy (see our previous announcement here). The event, titled "Science meets Diplomacy: a new European perspective", was hosted by TWAS – ...

[S4D4Cs Final Networking event \(online\)](#)

Between March 15 and 19, the project celebrated its final conference (the project ends on April 30, 2021). In the next few weeks ...

[S4D4Cs 2nd European Networking Meeting, Berlin](#)

The S4D4C event, opened by Tim Flink and Elke Dall of the S4D4C consortium at the Magnus-Haus (seat of the German Physical Society) in Berlin, contributed further to the visibility that the science diplomacy concept ...

[S4D4C's 1st Global Meeting, Madrid](#)

A truly global community of science diplomacy scholars and practitioners met on the occasion of S4D4C's 1st Global Meeting, which took place 12-14 December at the headquarters of the Spanish Agency for International Development Cooperation ...

Annex 6: S4D4C partners participation in events (selection)

[S4D4C partner at the Indo-German Dialogue – Science diplomacy for international cooperation](#)

On January 21, 2021, our colleague Maria Josten (DLR) participates in the Indo-German Dialogue on science diplomacy for international cooperation organised by the DWIH New Delhi. The event brings together stakeholders active in the fields ...

[Science Diplomacy in the Mediterranean: An S4D4C and Union for the Mediterranean Joint Event](#)

On the 15th and 16th December 2020, S4D4C and the Union for the Mediterranean organised a joint workshop to explore the role of science diplomacy in the Mediterranean. The workshop was attended by more than ...

[EU Science Diplomacy in the Post-COVID Era: a discussion with EURAXESS North America](#)

EURAXESS North America leads a webinar addressing the current state of European science diplomacy and various topics surrounding the challenges brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the opportunities ahead based on lessons ...

[Europe and Canada addressing global challenges together: science diplomacy as a strategic approach](#)

S4D4C has pulled together a panel for the 12th Canadian Science Policy Conference (CSPC 2020). The event took place during the opening parallel sessions on November 16. CSPC ran from November 16-20 as an online ...

[Report launch event: "Science Diplomacy in Latin America and the Caribbean: Strategies, Mechanisms, and Perspectives"](#)

Our S4D4C team member Marga Gual Soler has authored a new science diplomacy report for the UNESCO Regional Office for Science for Latin America and the Caribbean. The policy paper "Science Diplomacy in Latin America ...

[European Research Days 2020: Australia & New Zealand Edition](#)

On November 27, S4D4C participates in the European Research Days 2020 (#ERD2020) Australia & New Zealand edition. The European Research Days are organized by EURAXESS Worldwide which is a platform on researchers' mobility present in ...

[NanoSafety researchers: "Science Diplomacy: A New Way to Think About Your Role in a Community of Research"](#)

In the spirit of the nanoSAFE2020 conference, SAbyNA organises on November 23rd a training session on "Science Diplomacy: A New Way to Think About Your Role in a Community of Research". The first part of ...

[Event announcement: Falling WallsXBerlin Science Week](#)

Falling Walls and Berlin Science Week will host the 2020 edition of the World Science Summit, held remotely from 1 – 10 November 2020. The event gathers some of the world's best researchers which will take ...

[Online discussion: 'Joining forces for sustainable development' with Vienna School of International Studies](#)

"Science Diplomacy – Joining forces for sustainable development" was the motto of the latest edition of the zoom discussion series "Diplomacy – Your Questions, Our Answers", which is

regularly being organised by the S4D4C consortium member Diplomatische Akademie Wien – Vienna School of International Studies (DA) ...

Briefing Science Policy Fellows on Science Diplomacy

S4D4C is interested in the implementation of science diplomacy and science policy fellowships as opportunities to strengthen the links between these different worlds (for example, S4D4C has implemented its own small programme, inviting scientists to ...

Workshop: Reflections on the climate debate in Central Europe: Finance and science diplomacy

The countries of Central Europe are rarely in the spotlight when it comes to the climate debate, but they are increasingly vocal and confident actors on the European stage. What exactly is their role in ...

S4D4C researchers providing actors' perspectives – InsSciDE/The Hague Journal webinars

Our sister project InsSciDE organized a two-days webinar session titled "Actors' perspectives: Science diplomacy and the cross-sectoral impacts of Covid-19. In the 4 panels, different practitioners, scholars and stakeholders of science diplomacy discussed science diplomacy ...

Ionising Radiation Research, Social Sciences and Humanities and Science Diplomacy

On 3 September 2020, our S4D4C partner Lorenzo Melchor ran a workshop entitled "An Introduction to Science Diplomacy: Navigating the Complex Interface between Science, Technology, Innovation, and International Relations" during the Pre-RICOMET Conference which dealt ...

Careers beyond the lab: discussions at the European Science Open Forum

The bi-annual European Science Open Forum had been postponed from July to September and was carried out as one of the largest "hybrid" science events from 2 to 6 September 2020. More than 1000 people ...

"Science Diplomacy and Global Challenges" at the ECPR General Conference

Our S4D4C partner Mitchell Young (Charles University Prague) organised a panel at the general conference of the European Consortium For Political Research (ECPR) on August 28, 9.00-10.45 CET. It is part of the section on ...

S4D4C at the EASST/4S 2020 conference: STI, science diplomacy and international knowledge asymmetries

S4D4C presented a session on Friday, August 21, 3:00 to 4:40 pm CEST. STI, science diplomacy and international knowledge asymmetries In the frame of the conference theme "Locating and Timing Matters: Significance and agency of ...

Event review: International experiences and perspectives for Colombia

Science diplomacy is an emerging concept in international relations and global policymaking. It entails narrowing the gap between the fields of science and diplomacy, often perceived as belonging to different worlds. Bringing together actors from ...

Science Diplomacy Webinar series in Tunisia

At the initiative of the Tunisia-European Union Twinning Programme «Institutional support for improving the performance of the Tunisian research and innovation system», a series of three webinars on science diplomacy brought together diplomats and academics ...

Panama's Science Diplomacy Strategy: Current state and future challenges

On the 24th of June, the National Council of Science and Technology of Panama (SENACYT), in collaboration with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the City of Knowledge Foundation, organized a webinar to present the ...

S4D4C online lecture "Science Diplomacy in the Making"

Upon invitation of the TU Dortmund Center for Higher Education, Stefan Kuhlmann and Ewert Aukes (both University of Twente) provided the online lecture "Science Diplomacy in the Making" in the frame of the "Higher Education ...

Marie Curie Alumni Association Science Diplomacy Webinar

On the 5th of June, the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) organised a webinar on science diplomacy as part of their career development series. The aim of webinar was to give an insight into the ...

Online Event: Science and Diplomacy: How can one foster the other?

Two of our S4D4C team members, Lorenzo Melchor and Marga Gual Soler, participated on Monday in a webinar with the title "Science and Diplomacy: How can one foster the other?" which was organised and orchestrated ...

COVID-19 Crisis in Europe: A Failure of Science Diplomacy?

SciTech DiploHub, the Barcelona Science and Technology Diplomacy Hub, has recently started weekly online talks with science diplomacy experts and stakeholders to reflect on the implications of the COVID-19 crisis. Titled "#SciDipTalks", this series comprises five ...

Opportunities and Challenges for Science Diplomacy in times of COVID-19: Online conversation including S4D4C

SciTech DiploHub, the Barcelona Science and Technology Diplomacy Hub, is a pioneering non-profit public-private partnership backed by leading research centers, universities, start-ups, and public institutions that positions Barcelona as a global lab in science diplomacy ...

S4D4C takes part in science diplomacy lectures

Recently, S4D4C has received requests to participate in lectures around the topic of science diplomacy and we are happy to report these events: Science Diplomacy lecture series in Turkey and Northern Cyprus Turkey is one ...

S4D4C helps to build the science-policy nexus for sustainable development goals

Three main takeaways: The University of Bergen organised a science diplomacy workshop gathering experts and early-career researchers to discuss about how to bring scientific evidence to decision-makers in national and international settings S4D4C was invited ...

More training for science in diplomacy demanded at the European Parliament

On January 21, S4D4C had the chance to present its activities in an event for Italian Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) in Brussels. The event was organised by school4SID, the "School for Science IN ...

Tim Flink took part in a joint seminar of the European Research Council and the Research Executive Agency on Science Diplomacy

The European Research Council (ERC) is the European Commission's body to fund and support high-quality research in Europe. It supports investigator-driven frontier research across all fields based on the principle of scientific excellence. As such ...

S4D4C participates in COP25 disseminating the value of science diplomacy for a sustainable future

On December 4, the session debate "Science diplomacy for a sustainable future" was held in the Green Zone of the COP25 (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 25th Conference of the Parties) in Madrid. ...

[A vision for the future in EU-LAC relations: Science latin Diplomacy](#)

The EULAC Focus project organised a webinar on December 3, 2019 to which S4D4C was invited to discuss possible science diplomacy activities. The following report is a shortened version of the summary prepared by Gabriela ...#

[Second workshop on the "diplomatie académique francophone" –with contributions from S4D4C](#)

On 25th and 26th of November, Pauline Ravinet (Université de Lille, S4D4C partner) and Pierre-Bruno Ruffini (Université du Havre, InsSciDE) took part in an expert workshop on « La diplomatie académique francophone », which was ...

[Celebrating global science diplomacy and collecting evidence at the World Science Forum](#)

Several partners of the S4D4C consortium gathered in Budapest, Hungary, attending the World Science Forum (WSF) between 20 and 23 November 2019. Our partner Peter McGrath (The World Academy of Sciences TWAS / Inter Academy ...

[Transformative Innovation Policy: Implications from and for Science Diplomacy](#)

Conference report of the Transformative Innovation Policy Consortium's annual conference, 4-5 November 2019 at INGENIO (CSIC), Valencia, Spain – Ewert Aukes On 4 and 5 November 2019, Ewert Aukes (University of Twente, S4D4C partner) explored ...

[Observations on Science Diplomacy in the Danube Region – an event report](#)

On 30/31 October 2019, the Czech Academy of Sciences (CAS, presided by Eva Zažímalová) in cooperation with the European Academy of Sciences and Arts (EASA) and ELI Beamlines, organised the 10th Danube Academies Conference in Prague. The meeting was dedicated to two ...

[S4D4C contributed to the debate "Science Diplomacy: Connecting Science and Policy" in the Prague House, Brussels](#)

The Prague House hosted a debate about science diplomacy on October 15, highlighting also the S4D4C project and its results. A crowd of over 70 people attended the event organised by the Czech Liaison Office ...

[Strategic Forum on International Cooperation: S4D4C discussing with the task force on Science Diplomacy](#)

Elke Dall, on behalf of S4D4C, was invited together with other representatives of the Horizon 2020 science diplomacy cluster projects, to an event on science diplomacy organised by the Strategic Forum on International Cooperation (SFIC). ...

"Communicating Europe through Science Diplomacy" receives high interest at the Research and Innovation Days

A fully packed room was welcomed by Jean-Eric Paquet, Director-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) and Maria-Cristina Russo, Director at the Directorate for International Cooperation at R&I Days' session "Communicating Europe through Science Diplomacy" ...

S4D4C results presented at two academic conferences in Sept

S4D4C contribution at the 13th General Conference of the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) in Wrocław, Poland. On 5 September 2019, Pauline Ravinet (University of Lille) and Mitchell Young (Charles University) took part in ...

S4D4C Partner FECYT conducts a role playing workshop about science diplomacy in the summer school of 'SciTech DiploHub'

The Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT), a project partner of S4D4C, conducted a role playing workshop about the role of science diplomacy and science advice in the management of a crisis in the ...

Panel on Science Diplomacy at ICPP4 Montréal – Organised by the S4D4C Project!

The 4th Edition of the International Conference on Public Policy (ICPP) took place from 26 to 28 June at the University of Concordia in Montréal, Canada – for the first time in North America. Public ...

S4D4C Contributions at the European Forum for Studies of Policies for Research and Innovation (EU-SPRI)

Science Technology and Innovation Policies for Sustainable Development Goals The international EU-SPRI conference, one of the most important venues in Europe for gathering STI experts from all over the world, took place from 5-7 June ...

EU and Argentina discussing science diplomacy: S4D4C joins in!

Scientific Diplomacy exchange between Argentina and the EU Scientific Diplomacy is currently a popular issue in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), as illustrated by the recent launch of a national SD strategy of Panama, ...

[S4D4C discussing Science Diplomacy with Marie Curie Alumnis](#)

Elke Dall, coordinator of the S4D4C Project, made a contribution to the Career Symposium of the French Chapter of the Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) which took place at the Institut Curie in Paris on ...

[S4D4C present at the re:publica conference in Berlin](#)

Already for the 13th time, re:publica 2019 is currently bringing together the European digital culture community for a 3-day event in Berlin (May 6-8), convening to discuss both current trends and technologies in the digital ...

[Science diplomacy needed for achieving Sustainable Development Goals, conclude S4D4C associated partners](#)

The InterAcademy Partnership, the global network of science, engineering and medical academies – and one of our S4D4C associated partners – has been calling policy practitioners and scientists to its 2019 conference "Science and the ...

[S4D4C with contributions to the "diplomatie académique francophone"](#)

Pauline Ravinet (Université de Lille, S4D4C partner), and Pierre-Bruno Ruffini (Université du Havre, partner of S4D4C's sister project InsSciDE) participated in a brainstorming workshop on April 2-3, 2019, which was organised by the Agence Universitaire ...

[S4D4C at Princeton](#)

Pauline Ravinet (Univ. Lille) and Mitchell Young (Charles University) represented S4D4C at Princeton University. They presented in the EU Program Seminar led by Andrew Moravcsik and Sophie Meunier on March 6, explaining how science diplomacy ...

[S4D4C partner Tim Flink joins the UK's POST Annual Reception on January 29](#)

S4D4C team member Tim Flink will be joining a panel on science diplomacy organised by the UK's Parliamentary Office of Science & Technology (POST) tomorrow, January 29. The panel is organised in the context of ...

[S4D4C partners to chair panels on science diplomacy during the ICPP4 \(Montreal\) and the ECPR conference \(Wrocław\)](#)

Pauline Ravinet (University of Lille) and Mitchell Young (Charles University) are partners in S4D4C. In June and September of this year they will chair panels dedicated to science diplomacy during two major events in the ...

[EL-CISD Final Conference – Meet S4D4C at our sister project's last event on February 27 in Brussels](#)

The "European Leadership in Cultural, Science and Innovation Diplomacy (EL-CSID)" project (Horizon 2020) analyses the relevance of cultural, science and innovation diplomacy for EU external relations, locating developments in these fields in the evolving global ...

[S4D4C @ AAAS Annual Meeting in February 2019](#)

You can meet the three European "sister projects" related to science diplomacy: EL-CSID, InsSciDE and S4D4C at the session "Beyond or Despite Political Borders: Science Diplomacy and the Construction of Europe" during the AAAS Annual ...

[Science in parliament: An interesting initiative on the sidelines of S4D4C](#)

Our project partners at FECYT in Spain are one of the driving forces behind an initiative to improve the science advice infrastructure in Spain: „Ciencia en el Parlamento" (Science in Parliament) brings scientists to the ...

[S4D4C represented EU science diplomacy in Washington D.C.](#)

On 14 September, the global science diplomacy community gathered at the headquarters of the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) for the "Science Diplomacy 2018" conference and the 10th anniversary celebrations of the ...

[Discussing science diplomacy in Prague](#)

In cooperation with the Czech Centres, our S4D4C colleagues at Charles University organised a panel discussion in the Prague Old Town. The focus of the discussion was on the topic of 'Scientists and Diplomats: the ...

[S4D4C was at the BioVision 2018 Conference, in Alexandria](#)

Last week, we had the chance to take part in the biennial conference BioVision 2018 in Alexandria, Egypt. Articulated around the theme 'New Life Sciences: towards Sustainable Developments Goals (SDGs)', the conference was the ninth ...

Annex 7: Stakeholder outreach

[Insights from Commissioner Mariya Gabriel "Towards Science Diplomacy in the European Union"](#)

This article has been written by Mariya Gabriel, Commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth in October 2020. We are very grateful to her and her cabinet for acknowledging our project and its results. ...

[Stakeholder's Voices #7: Breaking barriers with Anindita Bhadra from The Global Young Academy](#)

Anindita Bhadra is the co-chair of the Global Young Academy, an organization connecting and mobilizing young scientists around the world. The GYA aims at empowering young researchers so that they can access international dialogue and ...

[Stakeholder's voices #6: A conversation with the Central European Initiative](#)

For this stakeholder's voice, we contacted Nina Kodolja, Deputy Secretary General, and Alessandro Lombardo, Senior Executive Officer of the Central European Initiative (CEI). The CEI is the first intergovernmental forum for regional cooperation ever established ...

[Stakeholder's voices #5: A conversation with the co-chairs of the InterAcademy Partnership: Peggy Hamburg and Krishan Lal](#)

For our fifth stakeholder voice, we spoke to Peggy Hamburg and Krishan Lal from our associated partner the InterAcademy Partnership (IAP). The IAP is a global network of the world's academies of science, medicine and ...

[Stakeholder's voices #4: A conversation with Alexander Sokolov, Moscow Higher School of Economics](#)

For our fourth stakeholder voice, we contacted Alexander Sokolov from the Higher School of Economics in Moscow in May 2020 through email. The Higher School of Economics (HSE) is one of our six associated partners ...

[Stakeholder's voices #3: A conversation with Chagun Basha, DST – Centre for Policy Research at Indian Institute for Science](#)

For our third stakeholder voice, we contacted B. Chagun Basha, who is currently a visiting scholar at the Department of Science and Technology (Government of India)–Centre for Policy Research (DST-CPR) at the Indian Institute for ...

[Stakeholder's voices #2: A conversation with Julia MacKenzie, Center for Science Diplomacy at AAAS](#)

Science Diplomacy is fostered through the work of many actors around the world. For our second stakeholder voice, we contacted Julia MacKenzie, Senior Director for International Affairs at the American Association for the Advancement of ...

[Stakeholder's voices #1: A conversation with Jan-Marco Müller, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis \(IIASA\)](#)

S4D4C members travelled to Laxenburg, to an associated partner of the S4D4C project: the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), an independent, international research institute which conducts policy-oriented research into issues that are too ...

Annex 8: Other issues

[Gender in science diplomacy and S4D4C](#)

Day of Women in Science – Women in Science Diplomacy The International Day of Women and Girls in Science is celebrated on 11 February and at S4D4C we want to use this occasion to briefly ...

[Shaping science diplomacy for Horizon Europe](#)

Horizon Europe is the ninth European Research and Innovation Framework Programme (2021-2027) and successor programme of Horizon 2020 which is co-funding also the S4D4C project activities. The strategic plan, rules of participation and guidelines for ...

[What everyone is talking about: COVID-19 \(and science diplomacy?\)](#)

We currently all feel united in our worries about the infectious disease COVID-19 and the socio-economic crisis that is following. The S4D4C team members are of course also concerned, for example we had to cancel ...

[Open Science Diplomacy to tackle the COVID-19 pandemic](#)

By Katja Mayer The Coronavirus crisis shows us how fragile and sensitive our living environments are. Everywhere taken for granted infrastructures collapse, or it becomes clear that they are insufficiently available or maintained. It has ...

[S4D4C's Considerations on 'How to Include Science Diplomacy Aspects in Horizon Europe?'](#)

One of the main goals of the S4D4C project is to support current and future European science

diplomacy for the benefit of European capacities, EU foreign policy goals and especially the development of solutions for ...

[S4D4C acknowledged by EU Strategic Forum for International S&T Cooperation](#)

The S4D4C consortium is excited to read the publication of the Input Paper by the Strategic Forum for International S&T Cooperation (SFIC) "Science Diplomacy": Advancing the impact of Science Diplomacy at EU and Member States ...

[The Madrid Declaration on Science Diplomacy as a reference for Swiss Foreign Policy](#)

The Madrid Declaration on Science Diplomacy is a result of the 1st S4D4C Global Meeting on Science Diplomacy in Madrid, after which project partners and participants published it as a charter to raise awareness and ...

[Current European positions on science diplomacy – a focus on the win-win situations for global challenges](#)

A recent publication of the European Commission (published on 23 September 2019) provides a comprehensive overview of what the European Union did for Research and Innovation (R&I) in the period of 2014-2019; and also highlights ...

[Pauline Ravinet: For a more diverse science diplomacy](#)

For this new researchers' voice, S4D4C team member Pauline Ravinet is answering our questions. Pauline is Assistant Professor of Political Science at CERAPS and is the Vice President for European Affairs at the University of ...

[What about diplomats? Insights from Susanne Keppler-Schlesinger & Maximilian Huck](#)

Science diplomacy is made of individuals of many different backgrounds, blurring the lines between diplomacy and science. In this researchers' voice, SD4DC team members, Susanne Keppler-Schlesinger and Maximilian Huck elaborate on the multifaceted role of ...

[The SCIENCE in Science Diplomacy: Perspectives from Peter McGrath from TWAS](#)

There is no science diplomacy without the substantial involvement of scientists. Scientists know that and have increasingly shown more interests in science policy. However, most traditional scientific training does not prepare scientists to interact outside ...

[Meet Maria Josten and Nadia Meyer \(DLR\) and Lorenzo Melchor, Ana Elorza, and](#)

[Izaskun Lacunza \(FECYT\) on the launch of the S4D4C science diplomacy online course](#)

Learning the practice: With the launch of its European Science Diplomacy Online Course the S4D4C project reached a major project milestone. After months of preparation, the S4D4C European Science Diplomacy Online Course has been released ...

[Meet Mitchell Young, Charles University Prague, discussing the S4D4C case report and the background of its preparation](#)

On the occasion of the publication of S4D4C's latest project outcome "Science Diplomacy in the Making: Case-based insights from the S4D4C project", we talk to Mitchell Young, assistant professor at Charles University in Prague, who ...

[Meet Katja Mayer \(ZSI\) discussing open science as a tool for science diplomacy](#)

On the occasion of the World Science Day for Peace and Development, November 10, which is dedicated in 2019 to the theme of Open Science (see information provided by UNESCO in relation to the topic ...

[Discussing science diplomacy governance frameworks: Meet Stefan Kuhlmann and Gonzalo Ordoñez-Matamoros, University of Twente](#)

Just after S4D4C's 2nd Networking Meeting in Berlin, a dedicated co-creation workshop for discussing S4D4C's science diplomacy governance framework has taken place on the next day. We have been there to meet the team behind ...

[Planning our next big event: Meet Elke Dall \(ZSI – Centre for Social Innovation\) and Tim Flink \(DZHW – German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies\)](#)

Planning the Berlin Networking Meeting. What are your ambitions for S4D4C? Elke: As coordinator it is particularly important for me that the project activities make an impact on the political landscape, for example to join ...

[Meet Charlotte Rungius, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies \(DZHW\)](#)

What is your role within S4D4C? I contribute mainly to the conceptual and the case study work. So far, this included the state-of-the-art report, the needs assessment and the conceptual framework. Until now, I have ...

Our "Researcher's voices": Meet James Wilsdon, University of Sheffield

What is your role within S4D4C? With my colleague Jasper Montana, also based at the University of Sheffield, we'll be working on a couple of the thematic case studies – particularly one looking at science ...

USING SCIENCE FOR/IN DIPLOMACY FOR ADDRESSING GLOBAL CHALLENGES

PROJECT PARTNERS

Centre for Social Innovation – ZSI (Coordinator)

Charles University Prague – CU

German Aerospace Centre,
Project Management Agency – DLR

German Centre for Science Studies
and Higher Education Research – DZHW

The Spanish Foundation
for Science and Technology – FECYT

The World Academy of Sciences – TWAS

University of Lille – ULille

University of Sheffield – USFD

University of Twente – UT

Vienna School of International Studies – DA

ASSOCIATE PARTNERS

Center for Science Diplomacy at AAAS, Washington

Higher School of Economics, Moscow – HSE

Indian Institute for Science – DST
Centre for Policy Research

InterAcademy Partnership – IAP

International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis
Laxenburg – IIASA

National Graduate Institute for Policy Studies,
Japan – GRIPS

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